

Deliverable 7.2

Dissemination, exploitation and communication plan

Version 2

WP 7
Deliverable 7.2
Lead Beneficiary: CIIMAR
Call Identifier: HORIZON-CL6-2022-FARM2FORK-01
Grant Agreement No. 101084651
Dissemination Level: Public

IGNITION – Improving **Green** Innovation for the blue revolution: new tools and opportunities for a more sustainable animal farming is funded by the European Union (Grant Agreement: 101084651)

Executive Summary

The dissemination, exploitation, and communication (DEC) plan describes the activities to be implemented and the means used to disseminate the IGNITION project and exploit its results. The DEC plan has been developed as a living document, which will be updated throughout the project. The current version was finalised in month 8 (June 2023).

This document also outlines the rights and obligations of the Consortium towards the European Commission (EC) regarding the project results, identifies the key stakeholders, and defines the communication and dissemination channels. It also describes the internal protocol put in place to manage the knowledge outputs and to ensure the exploitation of results.

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
SC	Steering Committee
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

Improving animal welfare whilst reducing the use of antibiotics is a current research priority to help reduce the environmental impact of European aquaculture. Disease prevention is also of the highest relevance to a multitude of stakeholders, including researchers, producers, policy makers, and the general public.

IGNITION will create new knowledge not only in the context of disease prevention, but also in the context of a changing climate. The goal is to develop new tools to mitigate the adverse effects of stress, as improving animal welfare will result in a higher quality product, in turn improving aquaculture productivity and sustainability.

In IGNITION, bioactive compounds extracted from halophytes will be tested in animal feeds. Genotyping and molecular phenotyping techniques will also be used as new and innovative tools for fish immunisation, particularly targeting early life stages. Special emphasis will be given to the development of biosensors and disease prediction through machine learning approaches, based on the study of non-invasive biomarkers for health and welfare.

Results from the project will have a direct application in helping avoid the colonisation and spread of pathogenic microorganisms, including multi-resistant microorganisms, in aquaculture animals. Ultimately it can have a positive impact on human health by avoiding the spread of pathogens through the food chain.

2. Role of the deliverable

The dissemination, exploitation, and communication (DEC) plan details the approaches used for communicating the project activities and for the dissemination and exploitation of project results. It is conceived as a living document that will be updated throughout the project. To guarantee the high impact of the project results and knowledge generated, DEC activities have been integrated across work packages (WPs) - WP2, which includes a business plan and bio-economic modelling task, and WP7, which is about dissemination, exploitation and communication.

3. Rights, rules, and obligations related to results

3.1. Ownership of results

The partner who produced the results is the one who owns them. In the case of jointly owned results, the partners will be deemed to jointly own those results if it is impossible to separate ownership for the purposes of applying for, obtaining, and/or maintaining the relevant patent protection or any other intellectual property.

When results are jointly owned, the owners of the results shall negotiate and agree in writing on the allocation and terms of exercising that joint ownership in a separate agreement (“Joint Ownership Agreement”). All protection mechanisms and the upfront cost allocation must also be agreed upon by the joint owners.

Unless otherwise agreed, each joint owner shall be permitted, on a royalty-free basis and without the other joint owner's prior approval, to utilise the jointly owned results for non-commercial research and teaching activities. Each joint owner also has the right to grant non-exclusive licences to third parties (without the right to sublicense) and to otherwise commercially exploit the jointly owned results, provided that they do so with the following conditions: (a) they give the other joint owners at least forty-five (45) calendar days' notice; and (b) they receive fair and reasonable compensation.

3.2. Protection of results

If protection is feasible and justified, beneficiaries who have received funding under the grant are required to adequately protect their results — for the appropriate time and with the appropriate territorial coverage — while taking into account all pertinent factors, including the potential for commercial exploitation, the interests of other beneficiaries, and any other legitimate interests.

3.3. Exploitation of results

Up to four years following the project's conclusion (data sheet, point 1), the partners who have received grant financing are required to do their best efforts to either directly use their own results or to have them indirectly utilised by another party, particularly by transferring the licence. Unless otherwise agreed in writing with the awarding authority, the beneficiary is required to use the Horizon outcomes platform to locate interested partners to exploit the results if, despite the beneficiary's best efforts, the results are not exploited within a year of the action's conclusion. The beneficiaries shall request the standardising body to include the funding statement (article 17) if the results are included in a standard, unless the awarding authority agrees otherwise or it is impossible.

3.3.1. Intellectual property rights (IPR) and management

The IGNITION Consortium Agreement (CA) follows the standard rules outlined in the Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement (DESCA) model for Horizon Europe. The CA defines the main options for ownership and the different approaches for protection and access to key knowledge. These approaches have been defined to allow partners to pursue market opportunities arising from the project's results. The consortium will follow the rules for IPR defined by the EC, as regulated and agreed upon by all parties by written signature in the CA.

More information can be found in the Grant Agreement (GA, article 16 and annex 5) and in the CA (article 8).

3.4. Dissemination of results

3.4.1. Obligation to disseminate

Each beneficiary is required to disseminate its own results as soon as possible by making them accessible to the public. If the results are constrained because of the protection of intellectual property, security regulations, or legitimate interests, no disclosure is permitted. To avoid any potential emerging conflicts, partners that intend to disseminate their new results must give at least fifteen (15) consecutive days' advance notice to the other partners, together with sufficient information on the results that will be disseminated. Prior notice should be sent to the project Steering Committee (SC) by email: Ignition_SC@ciimar.up.pt

Any partner may object within fifteen (15) days of receiving notification, if it can argue that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless adequate steps are taken to safeguard those interests. Objections should be made either by replying all in the notification email, or by replying directly to the lead author(s) and project coordinator.

Each partner has identified a key contact person who will be responsible for updating the continuous reporting log (available in the project's Google Drive, under '[Ignition project wide](#)' / '[5. Continuous reporting](#)' / '[Continuous Reporting Log.xlsx](#)')

3.4.2. Obligation and right to use the European Union (EU) emblem

Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars,

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information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, and presentations, in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies, or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the EU flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

“Co-funded by the European Union and the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, the Research Executive Agency (REA) or the UKRI. Neither the European Union nor the granting authorities can be held responsible for them.”

The different versions of the EU logo (in the different languages used in the Consortium) can be found in the project’s Google Drive under *‘Ignition – Project Wide’ / ‘3. Templates & Logos’ / ‘European Union’* and at: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en.

When the use of the emblem is not possible (e.g. scientific publications), the provided text should be included to acknowledge EU funding.

When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

For the purposes of their obligations under this article, the beneficiaries may use the emblem without first obtaining approval from the granting authority. This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

3.4.3. General data protection regulation (GDPR)

The IGNITION project website (ignition-project.eu), managed and developed by Science Crunchers, follows the EU’s best practice guide. It is fully compliant with GDPR by incorporating a [privacy statement](#) and cookie bar informing website visitors what IGNITION does with their personal data. Google Analytics is used to track traffic and monitor website use.

Photographs and videos taken at IGNITION events will also comply with GDPR, through the use of consent forms to be signed by all persons involved.

Further GDPR guidelines and implementation processes will be detailed in Deliverable 1.3 “Data Management Plan” (due on month 6, April 2023).

3.5. Research outputs

Researchers will follow the EC recommendations and guidelines on Open Science, Open Access to Scientific Publications, and Research Data Management, supporting a seamless and transparent knowledge transfer model in benefit of society and innovative economy. Peer-reviewed publications of results in Open Access journals are strongly encouraged. A comprehensive list of journals is provided by the Directory of Open Access journals (<http://www.doaj.org>). Furthermore, publication in the Open Access publishing venue for EU-funded research – Open Research Europe – will be considered. Researchers may opt to publish their articles in a closed (i.e. subscription) or hybrid publishing venue (publication fees not funded by the EC), provided that all peer-reviewed publications shall be deposited in trusted repositories, such as BioRxiv or OSF (<https://osf.io/>), with immediate open access and complying with licensing requirements.

3.5.1. Pre-publication requirements

According to the IGNITION CA, for all types of publications and dissemination activities where new results are presented, the prior notice procedure must be applied (see 3.4.1.)

3.5.2. Open access

The beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results. In particular, they must ensure that:

- at the latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, is deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications
- immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND) and
- information is given via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication.

Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements.

Metadata of deposited publications must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, in line with the FAIR (i.e., findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following: publication (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue); Horizon Europe or Euratom funding; grant project name, acronym, and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication.

Only publication fees in full open access venues for peer-reviewed scientific publications are eligible for reimbursement.

3.5.3. Continuous reporting

The beneficiaries must continuously report on the progress of the action (e.g. deliverables, milestones, outputs/outcomes, critical risks, indicators, etc.; if any), in accordance with the information demanded in the Portal Continuous Reporting tool and in accordance with the timing and conditions it sets out (as agreed with the granting authority). As such, all partners are expected to insert this information in the continuous reporting log, available in the project's Google Drive, under '[Ignition project wide](#)' / '[5. Continuous reporting](#)' / '[Continuous Reporting Log.xlsx](#)' (Figure 1). CIIMAR will be responsible for adding the information in the EC Funding and Tenders Opportunities Portal.

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1	IGNITION		Dissemination Actions		
2	Dissemination Activity Name	Type of Dissemination activity (What?)	Target audience reached (Who?)	Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)	Status of the dissemination activity
3					
4					
5					
6					
7					
8					
9					
10					
11					
12					
13					

Figure 1: Continuous reporting log for input from the consortium partners

Partners are also expected to upload the published article or pre-print to the IGNITION archive. All publications with a DOI, ISSN, or ISBN (not exhaustive) should thus be uploaded in the project's Google Folder established for that purpose ['Ignition project wide' / '5. Continuous reporting' / 'Publications'](#)).

IGNITION partners are responsible for ensuring that all their scientific publications are reported. This should be done as soon as the publication details are available and no later than three (3) months after the official publication date.

3.5.4. Patents (IPR)

IGNITION partners are responsible for ensuring that their IPR and innovation activities resulting from the project are uploaded onto the EC Funding and Tender Opportunities Portal.

The following information is required on Patents and IPR under the IGNITION project:

- Identification of IPR type and Confidentiality
- Type of IPR (Patent/Trademark/Registered Design/Utility Model/Other)
- Confidentiality (Yes/No)
- Application Title
- Embargo end date

4. Internal communication

To achieve an efficient collaboration and effective communication among IGNITION partners, a set of tools, channels, and templates have been prepared. This will ensure resources are equally accessible project wide, that people can easily communicate between teams and institutions, and that results from the project can be communicated in an organised and homogeneous manner.

The communication tools have been created and will be maintained by CIIMAR. These include mailing lists hosted at CIIMAR, Zoom, as the video conferencing solution, and a Google Drive for file sharing and cooperation.

The visuals, branding, and templates were designed by Science Crunchers.

More information about the internal communication tools can be found in D1.2 “Internal communication tools”, delivered on month 6 (April 2023).

5. Stakeholders

A significant list of stakeholders to which the dissemination and communication materials and tools will be directed has been identified. This clear categorization of target groups allows dedicated dissemination actions to be undertaken through specific communication channels.

- Farmers and farming support organisations: should see that reducing antimicrobials in aquaculture is advantageous, not only from an ethical and animal welfare perspective but also economically. Such sustainable animal production can be achieved through the use of feed with potent prebiotic compounds.
- Policymakers: covering regional, national, and European levels, these groups can have a strong role in fostering a positive economic effect on aquaculture.
- Feed producers and associated industry: are the main distribution and direct channel to primary producers, and thus relevant to future exploitation of the project results. Attracting the attention of feed producers and merchants not only contributes to the exploitation of project results but also eases the dissemination to farmers.
- Technology suppliers: ensure that future technologies are adapted to the products and services post-IGNITION. Their engagement can result in new business opportunities and in the opportunity to invest in new technologies.
- Universities, research centres, etc.: IGNITION will open up new applied research areas for related products and services. Involving these stakeholders helps ensure that they

will be aware of the project's scientific background and use it as a baseline for future research topics.

- Food retail: has influence on the long-term commercial viability of the project's results and outputs in the form of fish and shellfish products produced using the improved methodologies. They will have an important role in ensuring that fish and shellfish products farmed and produced are selected for sale and marketed as safe and environmentally beneficial.
- Consumers / general public: Ultimately, the general public will be the target for buying food produced with these methods. Making them aware that they are safe, healthy, and ecologically more conscious is an important step in ensuring their uptake.
- Investors: solutions offering increased sustainability and healthier products for consumers are a sound business opportunity.

6. Communication and dissemination resources

Detailed information on the project branding and communication tools, both internal and external, can be found on Deliverable 1.2 "Internal Communication Tools" (due on month 3, February 2023).

6.1. Visual identity and project branding

The project's visual identity and branding guidelines were developed to ensure consistent and coherent communication by all partners, both internally and in dissemination and communication actions.

6.2. Project presentations templates

Several templates, including a PowerPoint presentation, a deliverable Word document, and a Word document for meeting minutes, have been prepared to ensure homogeneity between IGNITION documents and to facilitate the preparation of final documents. They ensure that the branding guidelines are followed throughout the project. All templates can be found in the Google Drive, under '*Ignition – Project wide*' / '*3. Templates & Logos*'

6.3. Website

The IGNITION project website (ignition-project.eu) has been developed and is maintained by Science Crunchers. The website, which uses the project's colour palette, is visually attractive, simple, informative, and intuitive. It is used to promote the project, its objectives, and consortium and to communicate and disseminate resources and events. New material produced for the project will be linked or integrated in the website.

6.4. Social media

Social media is an important part of the IGNITION communication strategy. Twitter and LinkedIn accounts have been created and the content is regularly updated by CIIMAR. Notwithstanding, all partners should contribute with content and help grow the audience by encouraging both internal and external stakeholders to follow the project on social media. Facebook has been excluded as a communication and dissemination platform because it has been losing relevance and is not currently an effective medium to reach the project's goals. Instead, an Instagram account has been created to reach the younger community.

The IGNITION accounts are protected by 2-factor authentication and strong passwords.

Twitter account: https://twitter.com/IGNITION_EU (@Ignition_EU)

LinkedIn page: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/ignition-eu/>

For EU visibility, the Twitter and LinkedIn account banners contain the following EU funding statement: "This project is funded by the EU (GA 101084651). Tweets reflect only the views of the project owner".

Instagram page: https://www.instagram.com/ignition_eu/

Because Instagram has no banner, an initial post stating the funding was published.

A social media code of conduct is available as a self-standing document in the common Google Drive, under 'Ignition – Project Wide' / '6. Promotional Material' / '1. Social Media Code of Conduct.pdf' and in Annex A.

6.5. Factsheet

A project factsheet, describing the project, its main objectives, consortium, funding, and expected impact will be developed in the coming months. The factsheet will be designed to raise awareness of the project and promote its objectives. It will be used to disseminate and promote the project in workshops, fairs, and other events. It will also be available for download on the project's website.

The factsheet will be translated into Portuguese and other languages if required.

Once developed, the factsheet will be available in the common Google Drive under [‘Ignition – Project wide’ / ‘6. Promotional material’](#).

6.6. Press releases

Press releases will be developed based on newsworthy outcomes of the project and will be issued to appropriate media outlets (such as sector-relevant trade press, journals, and web portals) to raise awareness of IGNITION, its mission, and its outcomes.

Other news, such as event announcements and updates, will be disseminated as short news articles that will be uploaded to the project’s website, and disseminated through the project’s social media. The strategy is intended to ensure that there is publicity and media coverage at local, regional, European, and international levels.

All partners are encouraged to contact their institutional press offices and publish articles and press releases at the regional, national, and international levels, making use of their communication networks and channels.

7. Communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities

The goal of dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities in IGNITION is to contribute towards an extensive adoption and sustainability of its results beyond the end of the grant. Given the high potential that the project’s results hold for improving animal health and welfare while decreasing the dependency on antimicrobials in aquaculture, IGNITION is focused on ensuring that its outcomes and opportunities are effectively disseminated to the appropriate target communities.

A multi-step and multi-channel approach will be used in the IGNITION dissemination strategy to tailor the information and engage with different target groups, creating a multi-actor approach.

To maximise its impact, IGNITION will:

- Raise awareness and interaction among key actors in the different stakeholder groups (see section 5) on opportunities available to them from the programme, as a way to contribute to behavioural change;
- To show the benefits that project outcomes will bring to aquaculture in terms of improved animal welfare and lower use of antimicrobials, and the improved overall

sustainability of food systems concerning social / health, climate/environment as well as economic scenarios;

- To foster collaboration, between actors of the food chain and primary sectors, bringing them together for collective benefit;
- To demonstrate improved access to sufficient, safe, nutritious, healthy, and affordable food for all, through a food system more resilient to shocks and stresses;
- To create the basis for the post-project exploitation of IGNITION technologies and solutions.

7.1. Aquaculture industry events and journals

Ignition will participate in the major European trade shows and exhibits to inform stakeholders about the project outcomes. Events will include, but not be limited to Aquaculture Europe, Aquafuture Spain, and Seafood Global Expo.

Additionally, trade press publications will be created, with a focus on digital publishers and journals that are pertinent to the sector, including The Fish Site, Aquafeed, and Aquaculture Europe Magazine.

Some of those events will include specially designed workshops for those employed in the blue economy to educate and update welfare concerns related to climate change. New operational welfare indicators for shrimp, innovative non-invasive biomarkers, and machine-learning strategies will all receive special attention in pursuit of more sustainable aquaculture. Online workshops will also be addressed for training activities for students and researchers. The coordinator, who has vast experience in similar training events, will organise these activities. As a partner in the European Aquaculture Technology and Innovation Platform (EATIP), CIIMAR will benefit from the various events that EATIP organises annually with participation from key IGNITION stakeholders.

7.2. Scientific conferences

To ensure that the knowledge is utilised for other scientific and technical fields, the IGNITION consortium researchers will provide technical and scientific material at pertinent scientific conferences. The European Association of Fish Pathologists, Fish and Shellfish Immunology, and Aquaculture Europe are a few examples of such conferences. Because Science Crunchers already participates in the World Aquaculture Society's communication committee, that platform will also be used to advertise the outcomes of IGNITION.

7.3. Scientific publications

Particularly concerning the production of new technology and several aspects of animal testing, scientific outcomes from IGNITION are anticipated to result in outstanding papers and thus will be shared with journals in related domains. IGNITION partners will guarantee open access to publications. Additionally, project partners will consider Open Research Europe opportunities for quick and open publishing.

7.4. Publication in newspapers and journals

Articles will be prepared taking advantage of contacts from consortium partners around Europe as well as pertinent outlets at the EU level, like Euractive.com, EuroNews, and EU Agenda. Publications will be crafted for their target audience, ranging from complex messaging for trade magazines to straightforward information for the general public.

7.5. Social media

The project communication team will generate messages that may be shared and reach a wider audience by utilising appropriate social media. The project's existing channels on LinkedIn, Twitter, and Instagram will be the main focus, along with YouTube for audio-visual, once content is available. Podcasts will be shared on Spotify and Apple Music.

7.6. Project workshops and events

The project will address all of its targeted stakeholders, disseminate its results, and encourage their adoption across Europe through an array of events, including stakeholder engagement and policy events. This includes the co-creation of workshops, involving research, innovation actors, and organisations representing citizens, government policymakers, and the industry to promote the project.

- The first workshop will focus on results from a reduction in antimicrobials use (month 36).
- A second workshop will focus on policy and recommendations (month 42), to be held in Brussels.
- A final conference will be held with a focus on the uptake of products and solutions developed in IGNITION (month 48).

Whenever possible, workshops and conferences will be co-organised with other FARM2FORK projects or other European initiatives (more information will be available on D7.5 “Initial Clustering plan”).

To ensure the participation of relevant stakeholders at events, the consortium will utilise and recruit stakeholders via exciting projects (national, regional, and European), networks (e.g. EATIP), or other cluster platforms (e.g. European Cluster Collaboration Platform, ECCP). Events will be promoted via social media channels, the website, and partners’ newsletters, as described above.

7.7. Project website

The website will operate as a repository for all project information, which will include downloadable public deliverables and results.

7.8. Leaflets

Project leaflets will be prepared with simple information for use at national and regional levels. They will also be used as support at trade fairs and exhibitions, workshops, and other events. These resources will also be made available in digital format on the website as a marketing tool for stakeholders and small-medium enterprises, among others.

7.9. Marketing via existing networks

The consortium partners will utilise multiplier contacts across Europe, such as the Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking, Bio-based Industries Consortium, ECCP, EATIP, and European Regions’ Research and Innovation Networks.

7.10. Cluster activities and EC services

The IGNITION consortium has a very strong network of existing projects and initiatives, which can support the project’s work. In this context, consortium partners participating in relevant projects will be recruited to establish synergies and links, enabling smooth knowledge transfer and experience sharing (more information about the cluster activities will be available in D7.5 “Initial clustering plan”). Moreover, common dissemination activities will be co-organised to increase the outreach of IGNITION and other project results towards wider audiences and broader stakeholder groups. Of particular relevance are:

- Other projects funded under HORIZON-CL6-2022-FARM2FORK-01: Fair, healthy, and environmentally friendly food systems from primary production to consumption
- AQUACOMBINE (H2020 CE-RUR-10-2019), 2019-2023; Integrated on-farm aquaponics systems for co-production of fish, halophyte vegetables, bioactive compounds, and bioenergy. Experience in co-creating business models together with primary producers will benefit this project.
- NeoGiANT (H2020-LC-GD-2020), 2021-2025; Grape-based products to reduce antibiotics use in farm animals. This project provides contacts to primary producers, retailers, and consumer organisations relevant to co-creation workshops and the development of business models.

7.11. Business plans from the technology providers

The IGNITION technology business plan will adhere to the Global Reporting Initiative's (GRI's) standard guidelines and serve as a roadmap for commercialising project solutions both as a whole and for each extract. The plan will be prepared by the DEB and will carefully evaluate and show the viability of the business prospects by addressing:

- End-products: Definition of the end-products and potential uses;
- Market analysis: Market size, structure, segmentation, needs, potential vs. accessible market;
- Competition analyses: competing / alternative solutions, market position, Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT) analysis;
- Triple-layered business model canvas modelling: implementing the original business model canvas methodology with two additional layers, covering environmental and social issues, including job creation, improved resource utilisation, and political/social impact;
- Value proposition / targeted customers: Market needs, benefits for stakeholders, value proposition analysis;
- Marketing plan: Market targeting and positioning, pricing policy, sales/marketing strategy and processes;
- Sales, technical, and administrative organisation: Human resources required, internal organisational planning;
- Financial plan: Access to finance, cost analysis, sales forecasts, and financial results forecasts.

8. Key performance indicators (KPIs)

KPI 1: Number of participants (or interested, if selection is required) from academia and industry in IGNITION events.

KPI 2: Participants' evaluation of the IGNITION event, using questionnaires.

KPI 3: Social media reach, measured as the number of visualisations per project-related publication (per month) throughout the project.

KPI 4: Number of website visits.

KPI 5: Project representation in national/international events and conferences. The size of the event will also be considered.

KPI 6: Number of resources (e.g. roll-up, flyers) used in each event.

KPI 7: Number of non-scientific publications.

KPI 8: Number of scientific publications and their impact factor.

KPI 9: Number of cooperation actions between projects in the cluster.

KPI 10: Number of expressions of interest from industry and investors in IGNITION results, that result in communication between the parties.

Annex A – Social Media Code of Conduct

Just as when using any other means of communication, it's important to pay attention to the content before sharing. It's up to the Ignition consortium to ensure its privacy and publish only content that can be publicly accessible. Furthermore, to keep a good reputation and create an engaged online community that is friendly and thriving, it is necessary to manage potential risks. As such, the project partners should be aware, whether in IGNITION social media or their accounts when interacting with the project, of the risks common to social media and take the necessary precautions:

1. Be aware of the project's target audience, which may slightly vary in proportion in the different channels: scientific community, policymakers, and the general public.
2. It's advisable to follow projects under the same topic, particularly the same call, fellow partner's organisations and individuals, and accounts related to the EC.
3. Never share confidential or proprietary information about the project. Often, spam and phishing scams use social media to trick people into supplying personal information. Never give out personal or project information over social media.
4. Content may include announcing milestones, scientific publications, press releases, newsletters, and the participation or organisation of conferences and events. Partners/researchers should make sure that no private information or new results that are still confidential and/or didn't go through the prior notice procedure (see 3.4.1) are disclosed.
5. Preferably write in the first person. If your connection to IGNITION is apparent, make sure it is clear that you speak for yourself. You may, for instance, add "views of my own" disclaimer in your "about" section.
6. Be mindful of charged topics, where emotions may run high (such as politics, religion, animal testing). It is important to show respect for others' opinions. Discriminatory content or comments are not allowed.
7. If you identify your affiliation with IGNITION in your social media, your activity should be consistent with the project's high standards and professional conduct.
8. If you communicate publicly about IGNITION, you should make clear what your role is within the project.
9. Be mindful of your source material. It is important to credit sources if you are reposting or using content from external sources.
10. Unless approved by the Management Team, your social media name, handle, or URL should not include the IGNITION name or logo.

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11. Routinely audit your social media account to assist you in identifying troll accounts (accounts that spread negative messages, causing other followers to lose interest in the project and potentially stop following) and non-active followers as well as your most effective and successful followers.
12. If you gain unwanted attention from an online troll, simply ignoring the troll could be the best tactic. However, if it is a member of the public who has been misinformed and now has a genuine concern about the project, it may be a good idea to answer back with facts, to set the record straight. A few warning signs of a troll account may be:
 - An account with no profile photo;
 - An account following a high number of accounts, but very few accounts following them back;
 - The "About" section of the account contains vague information;
 - The account posts are all ads about the same thing;
 - Bots will never engage with your posts
13. If a specific account is spamming yours, a good option might be to ban the user. The ban option leaves the troll account to continue following you, but they can no longer interact with you with messages, etc. However, if it continues to escalate then the most reliable method to get rid of trolls is to report them. Most social media accounts provide this option.
14. If you are not sure what is appropriate to include in your social media account or any of the guidelines above are unclear, please contact the Management Team: grinnaqua_mt@ciimar.up.pt

General rules and guidelines on social media in connection to IGNITION

- Make sure the content is yours to share or acknowledge the source accordingly
- Ensure there are no IPR issues
- Make sure you correctly tag IGNITION or use #Ignition
- Whenever possible and adequate, use tag Horizon Europe or #HorizonEU to acknowledge funding and maximise visibility
- Never use offensive language, argumentative or illegal content
- Be consistent across all communication channels
- Try to include visuals in your posts (pictures/videos)
- Engage with the audience by using replies, retweets, or tags

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- Connect with and follow other EU-funded projects and the EC's social media
- Follow the news and use trending hashtags where appropriate
- Monitor the social media channel to measure the impact you're having

Share the social media activities and analysis with the project's Management Team.

Document information

Grant no	101084651	Acronym	IGNITION
Full title	Improving Green Innovation for the Blue Revolution		
Project website	www.ignition-project.eu		

Deliverable	Nº	7.2	Title	Dissemination, exploitation and communication (DEC) plan
Work Package	Nº	7	Title	Dissemination, exploitation and communication
Work Package Leader	CIIMAR			
Work Participants	All partners			

Lead Beneficiary	CIIMAR
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Due date of deliverable	30 April 2023
Submission date	07 September 2023
Dissemination level	Public
Type of deliverable	Document, report

Version Log			
Issue Date	Revision Nº	Author	Change
26 April 2023	0	Tânia Pereira	First version
2 June 2023	0.1	All partners	Reviewed
9 June 2023	0.2	Tânia Pereira	Make suggested changes
6 September 2023	1	Benjamin Costas	Accepted version
29 June 2024		Martin Syvret, Snjezana Zrncic and German Valcarcel-Resalt	Project Review
10 July 2024	2	Joana Marques, Tânia Pereira and Benjamin Costas	Updated according to suggestions

2024